

Social Media a Concern for Foreign Relationships with Neighbor Countries

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ABSTRACT

Indian Sub-continent, especially Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan were divided by Islamic ideology. Bangladesh gained independence from West Pakistan in 1971 with the unbelievable support of the neighboring country India. The present article attempts to find out about the recent time controversy through social media between these countries. In the 2023 Men's World Cup Cricket Final match India vs Australia held on November 19, 2023, Australia won by 6 Wickets. Here Bangladeshi young cricket lovers enjoyed supporting Team Australia but Indians could not take it positively. They think Bangladesh as a Muslim country avoids Hindus and does not respect and love them. However, the study reveals that 83% disagree that Islam is related to support. 59.50% voted that a player's behavior is responsible for the support of India and only 3% think that religion may affect supporting the cricket matches. Finally, an effective recommendation has been structured for resolving the crisis.

INTRODUCTION

Two significant South Asian regional powers, Bangladesh, and India, have a great deal to offer the conversation about prosperity, security, and peace on a bilateral, regional, and international level (Islam, 2022). Bangladesh follows the foreign policy that was formed by the father of nations Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman as Friendship to all, Malice towards none. The formation of Bangladesh raised several questions, among them: would secularism become the dominant ideology for developing nations; would India become an Asian superpower; would Bangladesh become an extension of India's market; would India establish a subservient government in Bangladesh; would Bangladesh become an extension of India's own; and would India realize the Nehruvian vision of a Greater Indian Union (Haider, 2009). Although Bangladesh has recently gained numerous developments in economic, technical, and infrastructural development. These improvements and prosperity have an integral partnership with foreign countries, especially India. Bangladesh bases its foreign policy decisions on its historical background, geographical location, and above all the continuation of several unresolved bilateral disputes that are essential to the country's survival (Bhardwaj, 2008). The friendly relations between India and Bangladesh were severely harmed as the 1970s went on by several issues, including the dispute over the maritime belt, Indian support for the pro-Mujib rebels, the sharing of the Ganges watershed, and the conflicts around Purbasha island in the Bay of Bengal and Muhurir Char, an islet on the river Muhuri that serves as the border between Bangladesh and the Indian state of Tripura (Hossain, 1981). But today for the abuse of social media countries have faced multilateral problems including economic relations, social disrespect, security concerns and break up of relationships. In the recent cricket World Cup final held on 19 November 2023. The world here has watched Bangladeshi cricket fans happy with the defeat of the India cricket team through social media. India predicts that Bangladesh does not like India. Thousands of students watched the India-Australia final match on a massive screen that was installed at Dhaka University. They began to celebrate India's defeat, and several of them could be seen joyfully dancing (Das, 2023). Young Muslims in Bangladesh are pleased that India did not win the World Cup. Why do they have such strong anti-Indian sentiments when India freed them and they rely on India for practically everything beef, onions, clothes, healthcare, and entertainment, among other things? (Taslima Nasreen, 2023). Several widely shared videos showed the delight of Bangladeshi supporters as they expressed their happiness after India's defeat in the Final match. During the celebrations, a fan was interviewed and expressed his satisfaction about Australia's victory. I am relieved that India lost! Australia won in India, which makes me glad because India is the team, I detest the most. For us, Australia's success is significant. Their squad performed admirably, putting a strong emphasis on fair play, while the Indian squad is known for manipulating matches. Today is the happy occasion of celebrating Eid. Consequently, citizens of India think that Bangladeshis do not love, respect, or support them. There have numerous combats through social media. An

opposition leader of West Bengal stated that we helped Bangladesh to be free and be a sovereign country but they showed their happiness not to win Australia but for the loss of India. Here it is predictable that they think that Bangladesh did not support India because they (Bangalee) are Muslims. Governments urge them to follow Islam, which they obey, thus naturally they develop anti-Hindu sentiments (Basu, 2023). Here the religion has been founded to create a definition against the controversy. There have been political tensions now because of the integration of the political leader over Entertainment. But politics should not be a part of sports and games (Lapchick, 1978). This may be dangerous when entertainment is a part of politics. So, Bangladesh and India should not have room for political aspects in sports. Though they are a strong competitor in games and sports. These two neighboring countries should build up a strong and meaningful relationship beyond games and sports.

Objectives

Clearly outline the specific objectives of the study, such as understanding the role of social media in foreign relations, identifying patterns of communication, and assessing the impact of social media on public perception. The study has been taken to find out the following objectives:

1. Why Bangladeshi people do not support the Indian Cricket Team?
2. Is there any Islamic matter in the context of supporting World Cup cricket in 2023 between India vs Australia's final match?

Is it the major concern of foreign relationships?

METHODOLOGY

I have selected an appropriate research design (qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods) based on the research objectives. The survey approach was used to gather data through in-person interviews and investigations (through Google Forms). This study has pointed out 'Why the people of Bangladesh (especially youth) do not like the Indian Cricket Team?' Dhaka University and Rajshahi University have been selected to collect data in the present study. A total of 200 male and female students participated in the research (online-based survey). Students have faced interviews to find the research objectives. The main purpose of selecting these two universities is to collect survey data because they are representatives of 64 districts in Bangladesh. The collection of student data in the designated regions ensures ethical order (privacy). Anonymous has been used instead of using their names.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Being close connected country, Bangladesh has faced numerous political and critical incidents including Social and Economic problems, the Farakka Barrage dispute, the Maritime Belt problem, the Muhurir Char Border dispute, the Purbasha Island dispute (Hossain, 1981). Although, the independence of

Bangladesh also made it easier for the ten million Bangladeshi refugees living in India to return to their homeland. These refugees had placed a significant strain on India's political system, economy, administrative capacity, and social cohesion (Jha, 2000). On the other hand, Myanmar and Bangladesh connect the ASEAN nations with India, while the Bay of Bengal allows the nations to access the Indian Ocean for offshore business prospects (Bhardwas, 2020). Bangladesh-India shares about 4096 km, which is the most significant aspect of building foreign relations between the two. Nevertheless, these two countries have faced numerous controversial issues. Small state security plans are simply survival strategies in a world system characterized by an uneven and hierarchical distribution of power, typically plagued by a fear complex (Majumdar, 2014). The history of the relationship between India and Bangladesh has seen ups and downs that are frequently referred to as "enigma"(Ghosh, 2011). Undoubtedly, it is clear to all that Bangladesh-India relation is not clean but there are so many controversies in the sense of regional interests. To be honest they have raised regional problems and these are not bearable. But the governments of these countries have tackled the problems. Nowadays the social media controversy has been created by some supporters like cricket matters. The people of the two took part in verbal combat through social media-centered cricket. In the cricket-mad country of South Asia, people had been talking about the much-awaited final as they flocked to eateries, bars, and cafés to watch the match between Australia and India (Pathak, 2023). The study of the boundary between India and Bangladesh extends more than 30 years. The nature of the cross-border problems between Bangladesh and India has been brought to light by this effort. In the context of the comparative border research framework, it specifically draws attention to the cross-border connections between Bangladesh and India, which will deepen our understanding of bordering dynamics and border policies on a socio-political, economic, geographic, and cultural level (Shahriar, 2021). The issues include smuggling, illegal immigration, and insurgents moving across borders, all of which pose grave risks to national security (Das, 2008). So, the main problem of the two neighboring countries has faced in recent years.

Result and Discussion

Following data collection, an analysis of the data is conducted. Numerous data have been gathered from 200 participants inside the two designated Universities. Several noteworthy discoveries will support the officials and students in identifying the issues and creating a plan of action to handle the issues.

Figure 1: The figure shows the age variation of the respondents.

The respondents in the selected areas are adults and they are most mature in nature. 90 students were between 18-22, 80 were between 22-26 and 30 were 26-30. Consequently, people in selected areas are so much adults and knowledgeable.

Figure 2: The figure indicates responds religious status.

Nationalism is the foundation of the modern state. The post-colonial states frequently use state-sponsored theories of nationhood, which accept different aspects like culture, language, and religion as instruments of homogenization, in their efforts to forge a nation or homogenous populace (Mahsin, 2004). Bangladesh is a multi-religious country. There are several religions but Muslim and Hinduism are the major. There are about 85% of Muslims, 10% of Hinduism 3.5% of Christianity, and only 1.5% of Buddhism

among the total respondents. This result shows that Muslims are the majority in the study.

Figure 3: The Figure shows the results of responses about the government's religious status.

Many academics believed that secular Bengali nationalism was deeply ingrained in the nation after Bangladesh emerged in 1971 and replaced the "Islamic ideology" practiced by neighboring Pakistan with a four-pronged state policy of nationalism, democracy, secularism, and socialism. The country's founders did not even entertain the notion that Islam would become a powerful political force in the country. However, Islam quickly became a political force and began to oppose Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, the self-proclaimed "father of the nation," and his corrupt and inept government (Hashmi, 1994). Islam has been used in politics but it has never been separated from the democratic system, it has mixed with political ideology (Ahamed, 1983). When we scrutinize the research data, we watch that the government of Bangladesh never unravels Islam. 83% of total responses recognize that the government of Bangladesh is free from inspiring people to follow Islam. Only 17% indicate that the government may give incentives to obey Islam.

Figure 4: The figure is showing people's perception on supporting their best one.

Today's Internet is dominated by social media and news portals, but it also serves as a significant platform for the public's opinions (Mahtab et. al, 2018). So, in the data, we can take the perception of cricket lovers who think people love cricket to be fascinated by their attitude, and performance. Following the figure 59.50% voted for Player attitude, 31.50% for Arrogant attitude, 6% for performance and only 3% think that religion may affect supporting the cricket matches. There the top reason is the Player's Attitude and the second one is the Arrogant mindset. This data indicates that Religion is not the most important aspect of support. So, Religion does not matter for games and sports. Robert Ellis develops a theology in 'The Games People Play' that revolves around contemporary sports phenomena, with a focus on its American and British expressions. Ellis demonstrates how modern sport can be argued to have assumed some of the roles that were previously held by organized religion by utilizing historical narrative and social analysis to enter the discussion on sport as religion (Ellis, 2014).

THE INTERVIEWS AND PERCEPTIONS

Based on the goals of the study as seen from the viewpoint of the University of Rajshahi and the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. we have conducted several interviews. These interviews adhered to ethical guidelines, and pseudonyms were disclosed. This part has helped us to analyze and find out the ultimate objectives regarding the existing paper.

1.

Ami Bangladesh ar pore varot ke saport kortam. Kintu varother kisu player amer valo lagto. Akhon ami varoter player der acarone ar oder support korte mone chaina. 2023 saler one day cricket a ami Australia team ke support korelam. Tobe varot cricket team ta anek valo kintu tara acarongoto karone somorthon passena.

This person indicates that he used to support India before. But he turned his support in the World Cup 2023 into Australia. Because of the behavior of the players of India. He recognized India as a powerful Team in the 2023 men's World Cup cricket.

2.

Abossoi ami Bangladesh support kori. Bangladesh ar pore amar favorite team South Africa. Ai team a valo maner koyekta player ase. Tai ami south Africa k support kori. Jehetu South Africa final a khelte parenai, tai final a ami Australia k support kori. Ai dolta kokhono final a hare na. muloto ami khelata k khelar jaigai rakhi. Ami India k support kori na tai bole India k posondo kori na amonta na. India amader protibeshi desh amader liberation war a tara help koresse. Tai tader ke abossoi somman kori.

My priority is Bangladesh. After Bangladesh, I support South Africa. In this team, there are several super iconic players. So, I support them. But South Africa is out of the Final match. That is why I decided to support Australia because Australia never lost in the final. The game is not beyond the game. I like Australia, but that does not mean that I hate India. They helped us in our liberation war, so we should respect them.

3.

Ami amar deshke valo bashi. Tai ami Bangladesh ke support kori. Desher pore England ke support kori. To ai bisso cup a England Valo korte pareni tai ami finale India ke support kori. India te anek valo Player ase, tara bisso cup a valo korese. Kintu final a oder favor chilo na tai here gese. India ar jonno shuvo kamona thakbe sobsomoy.

I love my country. So, I love the Bangladesh cricket team. England is my best choice team after Bangladesh. Their performance was not good in the World Cup 2023. Then I supported India in the final match though they have numerous talented players. Their performance was excellent but finally failed to continue. I hope they will play better in the next World Cup.

4.

Ami Bangladesh ar manush hisebe dehske abosoy support kori. Ar desher baire jodi bola hoi tahole India ke valo lage kintu tader player der bavohar amar valo lage na. aber India khelai anek somoy fixing kore jeta amar kase kharap lage. Mone hoi icc tader nijeder protishtan.

I must support the Bangladesh Cricket Team as Bangladeshi. If I were asked to choose any beyond country, I would choose India. But the players of India are not perfect in behavior. I also feel unsatisfied when they take illegal ways in the matches. They act as the owner of ICC.

5.

Amra kheladhula posondo kori anek age thekei, age Bangladesh ar sathe Pakistan ar valo protijogita hoto. Kintu bortomane Bangladesh ar India ar moddhe beshi valo protijogita hoi. Thai protijogi desh hisebe ami sobsomoi varother bipoksho dolke support kori karon sobai mile enjoy korar jonno. Bortomane Bangladesh ar India ar supporter der modhe je rokom samajik jogajog maddhome dondo dekhsi seta vobissot politics, economics ar jonno valo hobe na. karon duita desher moddhe parosporic anek support dorkar hoi. Bangladesh jemon India theke anek nitto poyojonio jinish amdani kore Varoth thik tader poyojonio ponno amdani kore. Tai dui ta desher moddhe kono rokom dondo thaka thik hobe na. khela dhular baddhome dondo shisti kora thik hobe na.

We Bangladeshi love games and sports. We have seen that between Bangladesh and Pakistan matches were very competitive before. But recently, we noticed that Bangladesh and India are the most competitive teams. So, I support the opposite of India to enjoy a match. In recent times I have seen that there are huge disputes between Bangladesh and Indian supporters. This indicates future political and economic problems. Because these two countries are indirectly dependent on daily commodities. They perform import and export every year. So, they should not create any controversy through games and spots.

To scrutinize this paper, we can understand that Bangladesh and India's recent social media conflicts are not Islamic. It is just related to players' behavior and supporters' mindsets. The countries' policy-makers should not take in mind that Bangladesh does not respect or love India. India is a country but Cricket is a

game. We must decide which is the most important game or country. We should not forget most of the young people support and like games. But people of these two countries should not face racism. It should be kept in mind that most of the people of these countries are friendly. We must make a good and meaningful relationship by forgetting disputes that have been created by social media.

RECOMMENDATION

Managing social media in the context of foreign relationships with neighboring countries requires careful consideration and a strategic approach. Establish clear guidelines for diplomatic communication on social media platforms. This includes content, tone, and frequency of posts. Encourage the use of social media for positive engagement, such as sharing cultural exchanges, joint initiatives, and collaborative projects. Develop crisis management protocols for social media. In case of misunderstandings or disputes, have a strategy in place to address the issue promptly and diplomatically. Ensure that all official statements and responses are coordinated and approved by relevant authorities. Launch educational campaigns to promote cultural understanding and tolerance. There also should be educational research to find out the causes of rumors (Hossan et al, 2023). Social media can be a powerful tool for disseminating positive information about neighboring countries and fostering goodwill. Collaborate on joint social media initiatives to highlight shared interests, projects, and positive aspects of the relationship. This can include joint hashtags, campaigns, or online events. Provide cross-cultural social media training to diplomatic staff. This can help avoid cultural misunderstandings and ensure that communication is sensitive to the nuances of each country. Utilize private channels for sensitive diplomatic discussions. While social media is a public platform, private channels can be used for more discreet and nuanced conversations. Schedule regular bilateral dialogues between social media teams of neighboring countries. This can help in aligning communication strategies and addressing concerns proactively. Establish a joint fact-checking mechanism to verify information before it is shared on social media. Misinformation can escalate tensions, so ensuring the accuracy of information is crucial. Create a digital diplomacy task force that monitors and analyzes social media trends and sentiments. This can provide insights into public opinion and help in shaping diplomatic strategies. Encourage people-to-people connections through social media. Facilitate exchanges between citizens, cultural groups, and organizations to build grassroots connections. By implementing these recommendations, countries can leverage the positive aspects of social media to strengthen diplomatic ties, mitigate potential conflicts, and foster a more positive public perception between neighboring nations.

CONCLUSION

Bangladesh is a South Asian country. This country relates to two neighboring countries India and Myanmar. India is a development partner of Bangladesh because from the beginning they have supported Bangladesh in the

context of independence. Bangladesh takes support and takes shelter from India so, undoubtedly India is a friendly country for Bangladesh. Bangladesh is a young and developing country. Recently these two countries have witnessed social media conflicts across men's World Cup cricket 2023. The complex challenges dividing India and Bangladesh need the leaders of both nations to exercise patience, forbearance, and forward-thinking to find a solution. People from these two countries create altercations through social media. There are still concerns between the two neighbors, but these might be resolved with active cooperation and understanding of one another's difficulties. Bangladesh has limited options, but if its national leaders use them wisely, the nation's bargaining position with India could improve.

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REFERENCES

References

- Basu, A. (2023). Taslima Nasrin slams Bangladeshis celebrating India's defeat in cricket World Cup final. India: Firstpost. Retrieved from <https://www.firstpost.com/sports/taslima-nasrin-slams-bangladeshis-celebrating-indias-defeat-in-cricket-world-cup-final-13414102.html>
- Bhardwaj, S. (2008). Bangladesh foreign policy vis-a-vis India. *Strategic Analysis*, 27(2), 263-278. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09700160308450087>
- Bhardwas, S. K. (2020). Tenets of India-Bangladesh Relations. *Indian Foreign Affairs Journal*, 15(3), 259-267. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48630187>
- Das, P. (2008). India-Bangladesh Border Management: A Review of Government's Response. *Strategic Analysis*, 32(3), 367-388. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09700160802063228>
- Das, P. (2008). India-Bangladesh Border Management: A Review of Government's Response. *Strategic Analysis*, 32(3), 367-388. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09700160802063228>
- Das, Y. S. (2023). World Cup videos spark debate on anti-India sentiment in Bangladesh. New Delhi: INDIA TODAY. Retrieved from <https://www.indiatoday.in/world/story/cricket-world-cup-final-videos-bangladesh-anti-india-sentiments-election-2024-2466740-2023-11-24>
- Haider, Z. (2009). A Revisit to the Indian Role in the Bangladesh Liberation War. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 44(5), 537-551. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0021909609340062>
- Hossain, I. (1981). Bangladesh-India Relations: Issues and Problems. *Asian Survey*, 1115-1128. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2307/2643997>
- Hossain, I. (1981). Bangladesh-India Relations: Issues and Problems. *Asian Survey*, 1115-1128. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2307/2643997>
- Hossain, I. (1981). Bangladesh-India Relations: Issues and Problems. *Asian Survey*, 21(11), 1115-1128. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2307/2643997>
- Islam, M. S. (2022). Bangladesh-India Relations: Fifty Years of Friendship and Partnership. *Journal of Bangladesh and Global Affairs*, 1(1), 107-122. doi:<https://doi.org/10.55875/jbga.bd.may22.006>
- Jha, N. K. (2000). INDIA-BANGLADESH RELATIONS: A PERSPECTIVE. *India Quarterly*, 56(3/4), 15-34. doi:<https://www.jstor.org/stable/45073231>
- Lapchick, R. E. (1978). A Political History of the Modern Olympic Games. *Journal of Sport and Social Issues*, 2(1), 1-12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/019372357800200102>
- Majumdar, A. J. (2014). Making Sense of India-Bangladesh Relations. *India Quarterly*, 70(4), 327-340. doi:<https://www.jstor.org/stable/45072806>
- Pathak, M. (2023). India vs Australia Cricket World Cup final: Fans slam 'mostly silent' crowd. Qatar: Aljazeera. Retrieved from <https://www.aljazeera.com/sports/2023/11/20/icc-cricket-world-cup-2023-final-fans-slam-mostly-silent-crowd-at-india-australia-title-clash>

- Shahriar, S. (2021). Bangladesh-India border issues: A critical review. *Geoforum*, 124, 257-260. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2021.05.008>
- Mohsin, A. A. (2004). Religion, politics, and security: The case of Bangladesh. *Religious radicalism and security in South Asia*, 467-488.
- Hashmi, T. U. I. (1994). Islam in Bangladesh politics. In *Islam, Muslims and the Modern State: Case-Studies of Muslims in Thirteen Countries* (pp. 100-138). London: Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-349-14208-8_5
- Ahamed, E. (1983). Current trends of Islam in Bangladesh. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 1114-1119. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-349-14208-8_5
- Mahtab, S. A., Islam, N., & Rahaman, M. M. (2018, September). Sentiment analysis on bangladesh cricket with support vector machine. In *2018 international conference on Bangla speech and language processing (ICBSLP)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- Ellis, R. (2014). The games people play: Theology, religion, and sport. *The Games People Play*, 1-334. <https://www.torrossa.com/it/resources/an/5262630>
- Hossan, M. A., Islam, M. A., & Khatun, M. (2023). Unlocking Student Creativity and Research Potential in Bangladesh: The Crucial Role of Policy Makers in Breaking Deadlocks. <https://doi.org/10.59890/ijarss.v1i1.256>
- Taslina Nasreen, Twitter post, <https://www.thedailystar.net/sports/cricket/news/english-cricketers-blast-taslina-nasreen-2073197>